

Transition Metal Complexes of Isonitroso-Ketones

B. C. HALDAR

Inorganic and Nuclear Chemistry Laboratory, Institute of Science, Madame Cama Road, Bombay 400032

THE work on transition metal complexes of isonitrosoketones carried out in our laboratory during the last few years is briefly reviewed in this presentation. The transition metal complexes of α -benzilmonoxime (HBMO) are also included in this review because the ligand contains the reactive group $-\text{C}-\text{C}-$, which determines the characteristic

reactions of isonitrosoketones.

The ligands containing the group $-\text{CO}-\text{C}(:\text{NOH})-$ in open aliphatic chains react with transition metal ions to form coloured complexes. Whitely¹ observed that isonitrosoacetone and other analogous compounds react with iron(II) sulfate in slightly alkaline medium to form blue compounds which are more or less soluble in water and form blue solutions in organic solvents. Feigl and co-workers²⁻⁴ studied the reaction of iron(II) salts with a series of compounds containing the group $-\text{CO}-\text{C}(:\text{NOH})-$ in aliphatic chains. They reported that the iron blue reaction could not be observed unless the ligands tested by them contained an enolisable $\text{C}=\text{O}$ group adjacent to a $-\text{C}(\text{=NOH})-$ group. They, therefore, opined that it is permissible to represent the blue colored iron (II) compounds of these ligands by the structure I.

This formulation is also supported by the fact that isonitrosoacetone methyl ether produces blue colour with iron(II) salts though it does not contain a free $=\text{N}-\text{OH}$ group. Considering that α -benzilmonoxime (HEMO) gives an iron blue reaction it has been

pointed out that the enolization of the $\text{C}=\text{O}$ group cannot be considered as essential for all cases in which the iron blue reaction occurs. It may be mentioned that the iron blue reaction is not observed with β -benzilmonoxime, apparently due to the steric position of the $=\text{NOH}$ group.

Ponzio⁵ reported the formation of bis (isonitrosoacetonato)cobalt(II) by the reaction of isonitrosoacetylacetone (HINAA) with cobalt(II) salts in neutral or slightly alkaline solution. Under identical conditions Taylor and Ewbank⁶ obtained tris (isonitrosoacetylacetonato)cobalt (III). They also prepared tris-complexes of Co(III) with isonitrosoacetophenone (HINAP) and ethyl- α -isonitrosoacetate (HEINAAC)(ethylloximinoacetate). On the basis of analytical data and assuming $=\text{NOH}$ group as the acidic group they represented the tris-complexes of cobalt (III) as in structure II.

where $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$ or C_6H_5
 $\text{R}^1 = \text{COCH}_3, \text{H}$ or COOC_2H_5

Pfeiffer and Richarz⁷ proposed the structure III for $\text{Co}(\text{BMO})_3$

General Behaviour and Properties of Complexes of Co(II), Co(III), Fe(II), Pd(II) and Rh(III)

HINAA(C₅H₇O₃N), HINAP(C₈H₇O₂N) and HEMO(C₁₄H₁₁O₂N) form complexes of the type MR₂ with bivalent transition-metal ions, where M=Ni(II), Fe(II) or Pd(II). HINAA also reacts with Ni(II) in ammoniacal solution to produce Ni(C₅H₇O₂N₂)₂. HEINAAC(C₆H₉O₄N) gives complexes of the bis-type with Fe(II) and Pd(II), while it produces with ammoniacal solution of Ni(II) a compound of formula Ni(C₆H₉O₃N₂)₂. Co(II) reacts with the above mentioned ligands to form neutral,

water insoluble, diamagnetic, tris-complexes of the type CoR₃ having octahedral structure involving d²sp³ hybridization⁸⁻¹³. An ionic complex¹⁴ of composition Co[Co(EINAAC)₃]₂ is also formed by the reaction of Co(II) with HEINAAC. Its composition has been established by conductance, magnetic and ion exchange studies. Nambiar and Subramanian¹⁵ inferred from the polarographic behaviour of Co(EINAAC)₃ that a bis-complex of Co(II) with HEINAAC is formed in solution. Some of the characteristic properties of the metal complexes prepared are summarized in Tables I and II. Haldar and co-workers have shown that proton magnetic

TABLE I—SOME CHARACTERISTIC PROPERTIES OF TRANSITION METAL COMPLEXES OF HINAA, HINAP, HEINAAC AND HBMO.

Compound	Color	Mol. wt. (obs.)	PMR signals in τ with respect to TMS	Electronic absorption bands in kK.	I.R. bands in cm ⁻¹	
					N—>O	N—N
1. Co(INAA) ₃	Orange-red	435	7.3, 6.8	40.00, 30.03, 28.73	1286	593 & 583
2. Co(INAP) ₃	„	506	2.75, 3.47	37.37(sh), 34.36, 27.77, 25.00	1203	628
3. Co(EINAAC) ₃	„	530	8.70, 8.60, 8.30, 7.2, 5.9, 5.8, 5.7, 5.5	43.48, 36.36, 28.67	1292	625
4. Co(BMO) ₂	Red-brown	733	2.50, 2.80	40.00, 27.77, 25.64	1290	610
5. Rh(BMO) ₂	Brick-red	—	2.35, 2.50	40.00, 28.57—27.77	1290	608
6. Pd(INAA) ₂	Green	369	2.60, 2.30	40.00, 25.64, 19.61, 14.92, 14.29	1275	613
7. Pd(INAA) ₂	Orange-red	366	2.60, 2.30	40.00, 25.64, 19.60, 15.38, 14.70	1265	613
8. Pd(INAP) ₂	„	—	2.45, 2.10	42.5—40.00, 32.79, 23.81	1240	540, 478
*9. Pd(INA) ₃ .2Py	Yellow-orange	—	—	—	1240	544, 480
10. Pd(BMO) ₂	Green	—	1.7, 2.2	40.00, 23.26—22.23	1290	590
11. Pd(BMO) ₂	Red-brown	—	1.7, 2.2	40.00, 23.26—22.23	1290	590
12. Pd(ETNAAC) ₂	Red	440	8.80, 8.65, 8.55, 7.45, 6.00, 5.85, 5.70, 5.55	49.07, 37.03, 33.78, 32.25, 25.00	1290	538
13. Ni(BMO) ₂	Red	—	2.80	40.00, 27.77, 24.70	1295	585
14. Ni(C ₆ H ₉ O ₃ N ₂) ₂	Yellow	387	8.8, 8.65, 8.55, 7.55, 5.80, 5.75, 5.70	32.90, 29.77, 22.73	1280	515
15. Fe(INAA) ₂	Blue	—	2.70, 2.36	—	1270, 1240	610, 580
16. Ni(C ₅ H ₇ N ₂ O ₂) ₂	Orange-red	—	8.45, 7.62, 7.56, 7.54, 7.50, 7.47, 7.45.	42.55, 38.56, 29.41, 21.75(sh), 16.69.	1282	628

*Insoluble in most organic solvents.

TABLE II—SOME CHARACTERISTIC PROPERTIES OF TRANSITION METAL COMPLEXES OF HINAA, HINAP, HEINAAC AND HEPO.

Compound	Color	Magnetic moment at 298°K (B.M.)	Curie-Weiss Const.	Electron absorption bands in kK	Infra-red N→O	bands in cm ⁻¹ N-N
1. Co[Co(EINAC) ₃] ₂	Brown	4.5	—	31.25, 19.61	Not examined	
2. Fe(INAP) ₃	Blue	2.86	0	39.23, 28.46, 16.67, 14.23	„	„
3. Fe(EINAAC) ₂	„	3.2	-62	16.66	„	„
4. Fe(BMO) ₂	„	2.17	—	40.00, 29.41(sh), 15.63	„	„
5. Ni(BMO) ₂	Green	2.82	-118	40.00, 27.77—27.01	1200, 1275	580(w)
6. Ni(BMO)AC	Green	2.25	-98	40.00, 30.75	1285, 1265	582(w)
7. Ni(INAP) ₂	Light-green	3.08	-152	37.04, 28.99, 16.81, 10.20	Not examined	
8. Ni(INAP) ₃	Brown	2.92	—	—	„	„
9. Ni(INAA) ₂	Olive-green	2.97	-32	15.87+	Absent	593, 587
10. Ni(INAA) ₃	Violet	2.63	-44	29.41, 28.99	„	592
11. Ni ₅ (H ₇ N ₃ O ₂)AC	Green	2.77	-44	15.62+	„	615

+Bands observed in reflectance spectra.

resonance spectra of the tris-complexes of Co(III)⁸⁻¹³, bis-complexes of Pd(II)^{12,14,16,17}, Ni(BMO)₂(red)¹², Rh(BMO)₃¹² and Fe(INAA)₂¹⁸ do not exhibit proton resonance signal due to the =NOH group. The absence of proton signal due to the =NOH group is interpreted to mean that the complexation leads to the replacement of the hydrogen atom of the =NOH group by the metal. Thus, the enolization of the keto group in HINAA and HEINA is not essential and these complexes cannot be represented by the structure I.

Structure of Complexes of Co(III) and Rh(III) :

The values of the chemical shift of the cobalt-59 resonance in Co(INAA)₂, Co(INAP)₃, Co(EINAAC)₃ and Co(BMO) gives the following order for the ligand field strength^{19,20}, INAA⁻>INAP⁻>BMO⁻>EINAAC⁻. They provide evidence in support of the five-membered ring structure III involving coordination through nitrogen and oxygen atoms proposed for Co(BMO)₃ by Pfeiffer and Richarz⁷.

Co(INAA)₃, Co(INAP)₃ and Co(EINAAC)₃, may, therefore, be represented by the structure IV.

where R =CH₃ or C₆H₅
R¹=COCH₃, H or COOC₂H₅

A similar representation was suggested by Feigl¹¹ for the structure of the tris-cobalt (III) complex of α-nitroso-β-naphthol. Nambiar and Subraman¹⁶ have proposed on the basis of analytical data and magnetic measurements that Co(EINAAC)₃ may be represented by the structure IV, where R=CH₃ and R¹=COOC₂H₅. The results of NMR studies are supported by I.R. spectra which show absorption bands corresponding to N-oxide linkage and metal-nitrogen vibrations. Rh(BMO)₃ closely resembles

Co(BMO)₃ and so the former is likely to have a structure very similar to IV.

The electronic spectra of the cobalt (III) complexes and Rh(BMO)₃ show $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions in the ligand and charge transfer transitions. The d-d bands are obscured by the high intensity charge transfer bands. The ultraviolet spectra suggest that the energy states of the π -electron system of the ligand suffers substantial alternations on complexation. The K-absorption edge spectra of cobalt in Co(INAA)₃ indicate two peaks at 19 eV and 29 eV corresponding to the transitions $1s \rightarrow T^*_{1u}$ and $1s \rightarrow 5p$ respectively. This is in agreement with the behaviour expected from the octahedral structure of Co(INAA)₃ and confirms its covalent character.

Structure of Pd(II) Complexes :

PMR and IR studies reveal that the bis-complexes of Pd(II) have five-membered chelated ring structure similar to IV. The planar configurations of Pd(INAA)₂, Pd(INAP)₂, Pd(BMO)₂ and Pd(EINAAC)₂ are supported by their electronic spectra. Pd(INAA)₂ and Pd(BMO)₂ exist in two colored forms which are presumably cis-trans isomers. The orange red or red variety has the trans-structure V, while the green isomer may be represented by the cis-structure VI.

where R and R¹ are respectively CH₃ and COCH₃ for Pd(INAA)₂ and R=R¹=C₆H₅ for Pd(BMO)₂. Pd(INAP)₂ reacts with pyridine to form an adduct of formula Pd(INAP)₃.2Py.

Structure of complexes of Ni(II) :

The five-membered chelated ring structure for the red-colored Ni(BMO)₂ is supported by its PMR and IR spectra. Its dimagnetism and electronic spectra indicate planar arrangement around Ni(II). The paramagnetic green form of Ni(BMO)₂ is octahedral. The two colored (light-green and brown) forms of Ni(INAP)₂ have magnetic moments corresponding to octahedral Ni(II). The octahedral environment is probably achieved by coordination through oxygen atoms from neighbouring molecules in the solid complex. The light-green variety dissolves in organic solvents to produce brown colored solutions. The brown colored species is dimeric in nitrobenzene solution. Its chloroform solution shows an absorption band at 10.20 kK ($\epsilon=15$) which is attributed to d-d transition in octahedral Ni(II). The two varieties (olive-green and violet) of Ni(INAA)₂ are paramagnetic. The magnetic moments and their variation with temperature suggest that they have most probably octahedral or pseudo-octahedral structure. However, the magnetic moments of 2.62 B.M. and 2.28 B.M. at 84.5°K for the olive-green and violet forms respectively are less than that expected for two unpaired electrons. The variation of fields strengths in the range 6000-9000 gauss does not have significant effect on the magnetic moment values. It is possible that some of the nickel(II) ions in the polymeric complexes may not have achieved octahedral configuration at lower temperature and exist in planar form. The ultra-violet and visible absorption spectra of the olive-green compound could not be measured because of its insolubility in most solvents. Its olive-green color is consistent with octahedral or distorted octahedral structure as indicated by magnetic data. The electronic spectrum of the violet form of Ni(INAA)₂ shows a shoulder at 36 kK in addition to a strong peak at 28.99 kK ($\epsilon = 2062$), a shoulder at 20.64 kK and a hump at 15.65 kK which is possibly due to d-d transition. The reflectance spectra of the olive-green and violet varieties of Ni(INAA)₂ reveal respectively a broad maximum and a shoulder at 16.00 kK which may be attributed to d-d transition bands. The infrared spectrum of the olive-green form of Ni(INAA)₂ shows OH-stretching frequency at 3530 cm⁻¹ and does not exhibit characteristic N-oxide band in the region 1200-1300 cm⁻¹. It, however, reveals Ni-N vibration at 592 cm⁻¹. The

octahedral olive-green $\text{Ni}(\text{INAA})_2$ may, therefore, be represented as shown below :

The structure VII implies enolization of the $\text{C}=\text{O}$ group in the ligand as indicated by the structure I cited earlier. The infrared spectra of the two colored forms of $\text{Ni}(\text{INAA})_2$ suggest that they may be considered as isomers. The olive-green $\text{Ni}(\text{INAA})_2$ forms an octahedral pyridine adduct of composition $\text{Ni}(\text{INAA})_2 \cdot 2\text{Py}$.

7.54, 7.50, 7.47 and 7.45 τ with respect to TMS. The six resonance absorptions in the range 7.62--7.45 τ are attributed to methyl protons. The separation between the peaks depend upon the field and so the occurrence of six peaks cannot be explained on the basis of spin-spin coupling. It is, therefore, inferred that at least three isomers are present in CDCl_3 solution and they do not seem to contain $=\text{CH}_2$ and $=\text{NOH}$ groups because proton resonance signals corresponding to these groups are not observed. The sharp proton signal at 8.4 τ is assigned to NH proton. Its sharpness is explained on the basis of the rapid exchange of NH proton with CH_3 protons in the complex. Integration of peak areas reveals that the ratio of the area under the peaks in the range 7.62--7.45 τ to that under the peak at 8.45 τ approximates to six. The orange-red complex in CDCl_3 solution may, therefore, be represented by the following structures.

On treatment with liquor ammonia the olive-green changes into an orange-red complex of composition $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)_2$. The orange-red compound is also obtained if the ammoniacal filtrate after the formation of the olive-green complex is raised to pH 10.5 by liquor ammonia and is allowed to stand for thirty minutes or so. Khatavkar¹⁸ has shown from conductance, magnetic and visible adsorption measurements that it is non-ionic, diamagnetic and square-planar. The first spin-allowed transition $1A_{1g} \rightarrow 1A_{2g}$ is attributed to the hump at 16.39 kK in the visible spectrum. The orange red complex $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)_2$ becomes paramagnetic in pyridine solution, the magnetic moment observed with $3.2 \times 10^{-3}\text{M}$ solution in pyridine being 3.36 B.M. at 303°K. This indicates that it becomes octahedral in pyridine solution probably by picking up two molecules of pyridine. However, attempts to prepare the solid adduct of pyridine have not been successful. The proton resonance spectrum of the orange-red $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)_2$ in CDCl_3 shows resonance signals at 8.45, 7.62, 7.56,

Other structures are also possible. Each of these structures can exhibit two signals of equal intensity for methyl protons but the total number of observable distinct peaks will depend upon chemical shift for methyl protons in each form and the stability of the various forms in solution.

Taylor and Ewbank⁶ and Djordjevic et al.²² have described the formation of red-brown and bright-red compounds respectively, which have the same composition as that of the orange-red compound. Khatavkar¹⁸ has, however, reported that the two compounds obtained by the methods prescribed by these workers have the same red color. The PMR spectra of the compounds in CDCl_3 solution are identical to that of the orange-red complex indicating that the same species are present in the solution of the three compounds. Hence the bright-red compound cannot have the structures X and XI proposed by Djordjevic et al.²² and Das et al.²³ respectively.

X

XI

XII

XIII

Its ultraviolet, visible and infrared spectra are similar to those of the orange-red complex and the red complex prepared by the method of Taylor and Ewbank. From these findings it is concluded that they have similar structures.

Magnetic and spectral studies seem to support the view that $Ni(C_6H_9O_3N_2)_2$ may be represented by the structure XII and XIII, which are very similar to those proposed for $Ni(C_5H_7N_2O_2)_2$.

Nickel acetate in ammoniacal solution reacts with HINAA to form a green colored compound of composition $Ni(C_5H_7N_2O_2)_2 \cdot (CH_3COO)$. Magnetic, infrared and reflectance data suggest that it may be formulated by the octahedral structure XIV.

XIV

The paramagnetic, green colored $Ni(BMO)(CH_3COO)$ appears to have an octahedral structure.

Structure of Complexes of Fe(II) :

$Fe(INAA)_2$ is diamagnetic¹⁸, while $Fe(INAP)_2$ ¹⁷, $Fe(EINAAC)_2$ ¹⁴ and $Fe(BMO)_2$ ¹³ are paramagnetic, the magnetic moments being 2.86 B.M., 3.20 B.M. and 3.17 B.M. respectively at 300°K. These complexes are all characterized by strong charge transfer bands in the visible region. Mossbauer studies²⁴ reveal $S=0$ state for Fe(II) in octahedral $Fe(INAA)_2$ and give evidence in support of the presence of both $S=0$ and $S=1$ states in $Fe(INAP)_2$.

References :

1. M. A. WHITELY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 83, 44.
2. F. FEIGL, *Oesterr. Chem. Ztg.*, 1923, 26, 85.
3. F. RAPPAPORT, Dissertation, Vienna, 1923.
4. S. TAUBE, Dissertation, Vienna, 1924.
5. G. PONZIO, *Gazetta*, 1922, 52, I, 285.
6. T. TAYLOR and E. EWANK, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 129, 2818.

7. P. PFLIFFER and J. RICHARZ, *Berichte*, 1928, **61**, 103.
8. N. J. PATEL and B. C. HALDAR, Proc. IXth Int. Conf. Coord. Chem., Zurich, Switzerland, 1966, p. 60.
9. N. J. PATEL and B. C. HALDAR, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1967, **29**, 1037.
10. P. L. PATHAK and B. C. HALDAR, Proc. XIth Int. Conf. Coord. Chem., Sydney, Australia, 1969.
11. P. L. PATHAK and B. C. HALDAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 745.
12. P. M. DHADKE and B. C. HALDAR, Proc. XVth Int. Conf. Coord. Chem., Moscow, U.S.S.R. 1973, N II.
13. M. S. GAIKWAD and B. C. HALDAR, (unpublished).
14. M. S. GAIKWAD and B. C. HALDAR, Convention of Chemists, Allahabad, October 8-12, 1972, p. 7.
15. O.G.B. NAMBIER and P. R. SUBRAMAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, **9**, 1138.
16. U. B. TALWAR and B. C. HALDAR, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 213.
17. N. V. THAKKAR and B. C. HALDAR (unpublished).
18. S. B. KHATAVKAR, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Bombay, 1971.
19. J. S. GRIFFITH and L. E. ORGEL, *Trans. Fraday Soc.*, 1957, **53**, 601.
20. S. S. DHARMATTI, C. R. KANEKAR and S. C. MATHUR, Proc. Symp. Chem. Coord. Compds., Agra, Part II, 157 (1959).
21. F. FEIGL, Chemistry of Specific, Selective and Sensitive Reactions, Academic Press, New York 1949, p. 254.
22. C. D. DJORDJEVIC, J. LEWIS, and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 4772.
23. K. G. DAS, D. N. SEN and N. THANKARAJAN, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1968, No. 7, 869.
24. P. H. UMADIKAR and B. C. HALDAR, Proc. XVth Int. Conf. Coord. Chem., Moscow, U.S.S.R. 1973.